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ЭКСПЕРИМЕНТАЛ ТАДҚИҚОТЛАР ЖУРНАЛИ

ЖУРНАЛ ЭКСПЕРИМЕНТАЛЬНЫХ ИССЛЕДОВАНИЙ | JOURNAL OF EXPERIMENTAL STUDIES

AKHMEDOV Farhod Qahramonovich

DSc, docent

Bukhara State Medical Institute, Uzbekistan

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MODERN ASPECTS OF INFUSION AND TRANSFUSION THERAPY IN PREGNANT WOMEN WITH PREECLAMPSIA

ANNOTATION

Preeclampsia remains the massive problem modern obstetrics. Is of great importance in problems preeclampsia aspects therapy. The Purpose of our study was: study of the condition of the system hemostaz and hemoreologi, estimation of the influence upon them infusion therapy beside pregnant with preeclampsia. On base of the work prescribed results prospectus of the examination 95 pregnant with preeclampsia. Depending on program conducted infusion therapy. Pregnant with preeclampsia were divided into 2 groups. The Main group has formed 58 pregnant, got preparations GEK (refortan 6%, refortan -plus 10%, stabizol 6%). Researched the factors vascular, trombositar and coagulation hemostaz.

The Track record of the factors vascular- trombositar hemostaz under influence infusion a therapy increase amount. trombositar was characterized by with using preparation GEK, observable was a shift in factor hemorealogi. The Results of the study coagulation hemostaz pointed to presence trombogen to situations. be accompanied expressed change the system hemostaz and reologik characteristic shelters. Transfuse decstran rendered the significant influence upon vascular, trombositar hemostaz and minimum on coagulation. The Got results afford ground recommend the solutions GEK to broad using under preeclampsia and eclampsia also beside pregnant with chronic arterial hypertension.

Keywords: hemostaz, hemorealogi, preeclampsia, chronic arterial hypertension, uteroplacental arteries, preeclampsia, central venous pressure, dextran's, magnesium therapy, stabizol

ИНФУЗИОН ВА ТРАНСФУЗИОН ТЕРАПИЯНИНГ ЗАМОНАВИЙ ЖИҲАТЛАРИ ПРЕЕКЛАМПСИ БИЛАН ОҒРИГАН ҲОМИЛАДОР АЁЛЛАРДА

АННОТАЦИЯ

Преэклампсия замонавий акушерликнинг энг долзарб муаммоларидан бири бўлиб қолмоқда. Ушбу муаммонинг ечимида даволаш асосларини танлаш асосий ахамиятга эга. *Тадқиқотларимиз мақсади:* ҳомиладорлик преэклампсиясида гемостаз ва гемореология тизимларининг ҳолатини ўрганиш, уларга нисбатан инфузион терапиянинг ўрнини баҳолаш. Ишнинг асосида ҳомиладорлиги преэклампсия билан асоратланган 95 аёл кўриқдан ўтказилди. Ўтказилаётган инфузион терапия сифатига асосланиб ҳомиладорлар 2 гуруҳга ажратилди. Асосий гуруҳни гидроксиптилкрахмал (ГЭК) препаратларини қабул қилган, 58 нафар ҳомиладор ташкил қилди. Қон томирлари, тромбоцитар ва коагуляцион гемостаз кўрсатқачи ўрганилди.

ГЭК препаратлари қўлланилиши билан инфузион терапия таъсири остидаги қон томир – тромбоцитар гемостаз кўрсаткичлари динамикаси тромбоцитлар ҳажмининг ошиши билан характерланиб, гемореология кўрсаткичларида силжиш сезиларли бўлди. Коагуляцион гемостаз текширувининг натижалари тромбоген ҳолатининг мавжудлигини кўрсатди. Гемостаз тизимида ва қоннинг реологик хусусиятларидаги сезиларли ўзгаришлар кузатилди. Декстранлар трансфузияси қон–томир-тромбоцитар гемостазга сезиларли ва коагуляцион гемостазга кам миқдорда таъсир кўрсатди. Олинган натижалар ГЭК эритмаларини преэклампсия ва эклампсияда ҳамда сурункали артериал гипертензияси бўлган ҳомиладорларда кенг қўлланишга тавсия этишга асос бўлади.

Калит сўзлар: гемостаз, гемореологи, преэклампсия, сурункали артериал гипертензия, бачадон-йўлдош артериялар, марказий веноз босим, декстран, магний терапияси, стабизол

СОВРЕМЕННЫЕ АСПЕКТЫ ИНФУЗИОННОЙ И ТРАНСФУЗИОННОТЕРАПИИ У БЕРЕМЕННЫХ ЖЕНЩИН С ПРЕЭКЛАМПСИЕЙ

АННОТАЦИЯ

Преэклампсия остается важной проблемой современного акушерства, что связано не только с частотой данного осложнения беременности. Целью нашего исследования явилось: изучение состояния системы гемостаза и гемореологии, оценка влияния на них инфузионной терапии у беременных с преэклампсией. На основу работы положены результаты проспективного обследования 95 беременных с преэклампсией. В зависимости от программы, проводимой инфузионной терапии беременные с преэклампсией были разделены на 2 группы. Основную группу составили 58 беременных, получавшие препараты гидроксиэтилкрахмала ГЭК.

При применении препаратов ГЭК динамика показателей сосудисто-тромбоцитарного гемостаза под влиянием инфузионной терапии характеризовалась увеличением объема тромбоцитов, значительным сдвигом гемореологических показателей. Наблюдались существенные изменения в системе гемостаза и реологических свойствах крови. Переливание декстрана оказывало достоверное влияние на сосудисто-тромбоцитарный гемостаз и незначительное влияние на коагуляционный гемостаз. Полученные результаты являются основанием для рекомендации широкого применения растворов ГЭК при преэклампсии и эклампсии, а также у беременных с хронической артериальной гипертензией.

Ключевые слова: гемостаз, гемореология, преэклампсия, хроническая артериальная гипертензия, маточно-плацентарные артерии, преэклампсия, центральное венозное давление, декстраны, магниевая терапия, стабизол.

Preeclampsia (PE) is an often-fatal condition characterized by hypertension and proteinuria at 20 weeks of pregnancy, affecting 5-10% of pregnant women. This problem is especially important in developing countries, where the incidence of hypertensive disorders of pregnancy is higher and maternal mortality rates are 20 times higher than in developed countries.

The etiology of PE remains a subject of debate to this day. The leading theories of the development of this pregnancy complication are based on the processes of defective remodeling of the uteroplacental arteries and placental ischemia, oxidative stress, excessive proinflammatory response, genetic predisposition and immunological intolerance between mother and fetus [1, 3].

PE belongs to the group of major obstetric syndromes along with fetal growth restriction (FGR), premature rupture of membranes, preterm labor and placental abruption. All these conditions have a common pathogenesis – incomplete gestational restructuring of the spiral arteries due to incomplete trophoblast invasion [6, 5].

Aspects of therapy are of great importance in the problem of preeclampsia. It should be noted that currently there is a clear dissonance in the treatment of preeclampsia. Thus, if in the study of pathogenesis there is a transition to research into the molecular basis of the disease, then in treatment the main control over its effectiveness is still clinical data; A/D indicators, central venous pressure, diuresis, state of uteroplacental blood flow and a number of general clinical parameters [2, 7].

The main principles of treatment for preeclampsia are the prevention and relief of attacks of eclampsia, restoration of the function of vital organs, and adequate and timely delivery. Treatment of preeclampsia has expanded with the introduction of new drugs [1, 4, 8].

Particular attention in pregnant women with preeclampsia should be paid to rational infusion and transfusion therapy.

Infusion therapy in patients with severe preeclampsia is usually carried out as preoperative preparation, during surgery and in the postoperative period. One of the main pathogenetic links in the development of preeclampsia is a violation of the rheological and coagulation properties of the blood against the background of hypovolemia. To correct hypovolemia, colloidal volume-replacing solutions are widely used, which can affect the hemostasis and hemorheology system [1, 2, 3].

For adequate treatment of preeclampsia, it is necessary to select the most optimal drugs that have a pronounced volume-replacing effect, the ability to remain in the bloodstream for a long time in conditions of increased endothelial permeability, the possibility of use in arterial hypertension and having a minimal number of side effects.

The purpose of our study was to study the state of the hemostatic system and hemorheology, assess the effect of infusion therapy on them in pregnant women with preeclampsia.

Indicators of vascular, platelet and coagulation hemostasis were studied (blood clotting time according to Sukharev, prothrombin index, amount of fibrinogen according to the method of R.A. Rutberg 1961, fibrinolysis according to B.I. Kuznik 1962, ethanol test).

The work is based on the results of a prospective examination of 95 pregnant women with preeclampsia. For comparison, 35 healthy pregnant women were examined. All women were comparable in terms of gestational age (28-40 weeks) and age (from 17 to 40 years, average age was 28.5 ± 0.22 years).

The treatment of pregnant women with preeclampsia was based on a complex of traditional therapy proposed by V.N. Serov (2002): sedatives, antihypertensive drugs, magnesium therapy, antiplatelet agents, antioxidants, cell membrane stabilizers, with the mandatory inclusion of infusion therapy.

Depending on the program of infusion therapy, pregnant women with preeclampsia were divided into 2 groups. The main group consisted of 58 pregnant women who received hydroxyethyl starch preparations GEK (refortan 6%, refortan plus 10%, stabizol 6%). The daily dose of the drug was 500 ml.

Repeated infusions of solutions of Refortan 6 and 10% were carried out every other day while signs of deficit in circulating blood volume persisted, stabizol 6% - after 2-3 days until hypovolemia and hemoconcentration were eliminated. The control group included 27 pregnant women who received standard colloids (dextran's) as part of infusion therapy.

The obtained data were processed by the method of variation statistics and calculation, the arithmetic mean of the sample population and the Student's reliability coefficient.

Initial changes in primary hemostasis in mild preeclampsia were insignificant. Disturbances in the hemostatic system and hemorheology have been identified in severe preeclampsia.

With mild preeclampsia, a decrease in the platelet count was noted in the main group to 176.4 ± 15.4 ($p > 0.05$), in the control group to 192.5 ± 18.2 ($p > 0.05$), severe preeclampsia, respectively, to 171.3 ± 16.2 and 169.3 ± 14.3 ($p > 0.05$).

Bleeding time in pregnant women with mild PE and severe PE did not differ from normal values. Indicators characterizing enzymatic hemostasis reflected a tendency towards hypercoagulability.

The blood clotting time in patients with mild PE was 5.6 ± 0.68 minutes in the main group; in pregnant women with severe PE, it was 4.8 ± 0.50 minutes, respectively. The prothrombin index in mild PE is $112.4 \pm 10.5\%$, in severe PE 99.2 ± 10.3 , and in the control group $114 \pm 15.3\%$.

Despite hemoconcentration, the level of fibrinogen did not differ from the level in healthy pregnant women (3368 ± 225 mg/ml) and was 3109 ± 323.1 mg/ml for mild PE in the main group, 3142 ± 372.4 mg/ml for the control group, and 3142 ± 372.4 mg/ml for severe PE, respectively. 3296 ± 475.5 and 3272 ± 386.2 mg/ml.

It should be noted that some patients had hypofibrinogenemia, which may be associated with the consumption of fibrinogen during the process of intravascular coagulation.

This our judgment is confirmed by the activation of fibrinolysis and the results of the ethanol test. Fibrinolytic activity increased with mild PE to $13.2 \pm 1.86\%$ in the main group and to $12.9 \pm 1.66\%$ in the control group, with severe PE - to $31.5 \pm 4.2\%$ and 26.2 , respectively $\pm 3.6\%$. In 10% of women in the main group and in 5% in the control group, the ethanol test was positive.

The dynamics of indicators of vascular-platelet hemostasis under the influence of infusion therapy with the use of GEK drugs was characterized by an increase in the number of platelets. Thus, with mild PE in the main group, this indicator increased by 10% by the 6th day of therapy (193.4 ± 15.4). In the control group, the platelet count continued to decrease and amounted to 194.8 ± 24.5 , which is 1% less than the initial data. In case of severe PE, on the 6th day of treatment, the platelet content in the main group was 211.3 ± 25.1 , in the control group 175.5 ± 20.6 , which is respectively 35.1 and 21% more than the baseline level.

Shifts in hemorheology indicators were very noticeable. Already on the 1st day of infusion therapy, a decrease in hematocrit level was noted. Thus, with mild PE in the main group, this indicator decreased by 12.4%; in the control group, 9.3%; with severe PE, by 6.2% and 4.1%, respectively.

The results of the study of coagulation hemostasis indicated the presence of a thrombogenic situation. A change in blood clotting time was noted, which increased by the 3rd day of therapy for mild PE in the main group by 5.4% (15.9 ± 0.8), in the control group - by 3.85 (5.5 ± 0.59 min), with severe PE, respectively, by 41.2% (7.2 ± 0.8 min) and 36% 6.8 ± 0.81 min. The prothrombin index at all stages of treatment was not significantly different from the value in healthy pregnant women.

The therapy contributed to a decrease in fibrinogen concentration. By the 5th day of treatment, this indicator decreased with mild PE in the main group by 10% (2783 ± 343.2), in the control group by 16.6% (2629 ± 312.6 mg/ml), with severe PE - respectively, by 13.8% (2842 ± 423.1 mg/ml), and 16.4% (2737 ± 387.5 mg/ml).

In pregnant women with mild PE, the fibrinolysis rate at all stages of treatment did not differ significantly from healthy pregnant women. In severe PE, there was a clear trend towards a decrease in fibrinolysis in both groups. In the main group, fibrinolysis activity decreased by 26.7% (23.1 ± 3.1) by the 3rd day of therapy, and in the control group by 2.7% (25.6 ± 3.7).

In pregnant women with mild PE, the fibrinolysis rate at all stages of treatment did not differ significantly from the level in healthy pregnant women.

Thus, severe preeclampsia is accompanied by pronounced changes in the hemostatic system and rheological properties of blood. Dextran transfusion had a significant effect on vascular and platelet hemostasis and a minimal effect on coagulation. The hemodilution effect, a decrease in the aggregation activity of platelets and erythrocytes, led to a decrease in blood viscosity. However, it should be noted that even on the 5-6th day of treatment the indicator did not reach normal values, which, apparently, was associated with the elimination of colloids from the vascular bed and an increase in hematocrit. GEK solutions improved the rheological properties of blood by eliminating hemoconcentration and did not affect the state of coagulation hemostasis.

Thus, the above results give grounds to recommend GEK solutions for widespread use as a first-choice drug in conditions of generalized endothelial damage, preeclampsia and eclampsia, and also in pregnant women with chronic arterial hypertension.

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Таҳририят манзили: 100152, Тошкент шаҳри, Учтепа тумани, “Ватан” МФЙ, Чилонзор 24-мавзеси, 2-уй.

Телефон номер: +99894-410 11 55

Эл. почта: tahririyat@imfaktor.uz

Веб-сайт: www.imfaktor.uz